

Modeling Voltage-Sensitive Dye Responses in the Visual Cortex to Retinal Neuromorphic Microstimulation in Mouse Brain Slices

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Abstract: Previous clinical studies have shown that electrical pulse trains delivered into the visual cortex can evoke artificial visual sensations in individuals with acquired blindness, demonstrating the feasibility of intracortical visual prostheses. Our previous physiological experiments in mouse brain slices revealed that a single microstimulation pulse can drive synchronized neuronal action potentials in the vicinity of stimulating microelectrode tip, enabling temporal control of cortical activity using retinal spike-timing-based pulse sequences. In this study, we developed a linear–nonlinear cascade model to predict cortical responses to such neuromorphic stimulation, and confirmed its ability to reproduce key features of the observed neural dynamics.

Keywords: Visual Prosthesis, Intracortical Microstimulation, Neuromorphic Spike, Physiological Experiment, Model Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Intracortical microstimulation has been investigated in clinical trials of visual prostheses as a means to elicit artificial visual sensations, known as phosphenes, in individuals with acquired blindness [1]. These studies typically employed trains of electrical pulses delivered to the primary visual cortex (V1) at fixed frequencies of 100–200 Hz, with durations exceeding several hundred milliseconds, to produce psychophysically detectable responses. However, how cortical circuits respond to temporally structured stimulation patterns at shorter timescales, and how such responses may contribute to efficient information encoding, remain little understood.

In our previous physiological experiments using voltage-sensitive dye (VSD) imaging in mouse brain slices, a single current pulse delivered through a microelectrode inserted into V1 was found to evoke synchronized action potentials in local neuronal populations near the stimulation site [2]. This finding suggests that cortical neural activity can be driven on a timescale of tens of milliseconds by applying current pulses patterned after retinal spike-timing sequences [3][4]. Building on this concept, the present study aimed to quantitatively model cortical responses to such retinal neuromorphic microstimulation. Specifically, a linear–nonlinear (L–N) cascade model [5] was constructed from the VSD imaging data, and its

performance in replicating the observed spatio-temporal dynamics was evaluated.

II. METHODS

A. Physiology

All animal procedures were approved by the Animal Experiment Committee of Mie University and conducted in accordance with international guidelines for animal welfare. Experimental methods followed our previous studies [2][6]. Coronal brain slices (0.3 mm thick) containing V1, identified based on a standard mouse brain atlas, were prepared from 3–4-week-old C57BL/6J mice ($n = 8$) and stained with the voltage-sensitive dye NK3630 in oxygenated artificial cerebrospinal fluid (aCSF) to measure neuronal membrane potential changes.

Cathodic-first biphasic current pulses (10 μ A/phase, 0.2 ms/phase) were applied through the tip of a glass micropipette electrode (tip diameter ~ 6 μ m, tip resistance ~ 1 M Ω , filled with aCSF) inserted 0.1–0.15 mm below the cut surface into layer IV of V1, which was identified based on cortical depth and cellular and laminar morphologies [2]. The temporal sequence of the current pulses was patterned after spike timings recorded from a mouse off-transient alpha retinal ganglion cell responding to random-sequence light stimuli.

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VSD imaging covered a $154 \times 820 \mu\text{m}$ region along the dorsoventral axis (see Fig. 2A) and was acquired with an EM-CCD camera at 1000 fps (binned to 12×64 pixels). The recordings were averaged over 50–200 repetitions per stimulus pulse sequence for each slice. Image data were converted to relative changes in transmitted light intensity (i.e., $\Delta T(t_n)/T_0$, referred to as the “VSD signal” [2]) and analyzed offline.

B. Modeling

The L–N modeling framework (Wiener system) [5] was employed to predict cortical VSD responses from recorded retinal spike trains. A block diagram of the model is shown in Fig. 1.

First, a “Lorentzian spike train” was generated by convolving a temporal Lorentzian function (full-width at half-maximum ≈ 0.49 ms) with each spike time in the retinal spike train. The Lorentz function parameter was derived from spike timing variability measured from isolated somata of mouse retinal ganglion cells, thereby incorporating the stochastic nature of spike firing [7].

Second, a “generator potential” signal was computed by convolving the Lorentzian spike train with a temporal linear filter, which was obtained as the cross-correlation function between the Lorentzian spike train and the measured VSD waveform over a time window

from -150 to 500 ms.

Third, the predicted VSD signal was generated by applying a nonlinear gain function to the generator potential. This nonlinear function was derived by fitting the relationship between the generator potential and the corresponding measured VSD signal using a combined sigmoidal–exponential function, with parameters estimated by nonlinear least-squares fitting.

To estimate the linear filter and the nonlinear gain, 16 segments of retinal spike trains and their corresponding VSD imaging data were used, with each segment lasting approximately 1.2–1.5 seconds. The VSD data for each segment were averaged across 1–3 different tissue slices, and model performance was evaluated using the same dataset.

III. RESULTS

A. Cortical VSD Response to Retinal Neuromorphic Microstimulation

Time-series images of VSD signals elicited by retinal spike-timing-based current pulses were acquired from the visual cortex in mouse brain slices. Fig. 2A shows a representative transmitted-light image of the tissue slice at low magnification (upper), along with a magnified view of a portion of the V1 region (lower). The imaging

Fig. 1 Proposed L–N cascade model

Fig. 2 VSD imaging of cortical responses to retinal spike-timing-based current-pulse train

area is outlined by a red rectangle, and the stimulating electrode tip is indicated by an arrowhead.

agreement was observed between the experimental data and the model predictions, although discrepancies

Fig. 3 Comparison of cortex VSD responses between experimental data and model prediction

Fig. 2B presents (a) a representative retinal spike train used to generate the temporal stimulus sequence of current pulses and (b) a space–time plot of the resulting VSD signal, representing neural voltage responses elicited by the stimulus shown in (a). To construct the space–time plot, image pixels along the short axis (12 pixels) were averaged to obtain a one-dimensional profile of the VSD signal along the dorsoventral axis (64 pixels), and these one-dimensional VSD response profiles were sequentially arranged over time. As shown, membrane depolarization, reflected by an increase in $\Delta T(t_i)/T_0$, was elicited by each spike cluster near the stimulation site in layer IV and propagated toward layer II/III as well as layer V.

Fig. 2C shows the time course of the VSD signal averaged over an 11×11 -pixel region near the stimulating electrode tip. For spike clusters with shorter inter-spike intervals and/or larger spike counts, increases in depolarization amplitude and/or duration were observed.

B. Model Response to the Retinal Neuromorphic Microstimulation

To examine whether the experimentally observed VSD responses described above could be captured by a simple descriptive model, we compared the measured responses to predictions from the proposed L–N model.

Fig. 3A shows two representative examples of VSD response time courses, with experimental measurements (dotted lines) and corresponding model predictions (solid lines). In both examples, (a) and (b), good overall

agreement was observed between the experimental data and the model predictions, although discrepancies appeared in specific phases. These discrepancies included the decay phase of depolarization following the first spike cluster in both (a) and (b), as well as the rising phase of depolarization in response to spike clusters of relatively long duration, around the 0.7- and 1.2-second time points in (a). In the latter case, the depolarization tended to saturate in amplitude during prolonged stimulation, consistent with the possibility that preceding responses inhibited or inactivated subsequent depolarizations [6].

Fig. 3B shows a scatter plot of the predicted VSD signals versus the corresponding measured values, with a linear regression line superimposed (dashed line). The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.795 ($p \approx 0$, $n = 16$ segments). Each of the spike-timing sequences shown in Fig. 3A was applied to three different slice samples. The root mean squared errors (RMSEs) between the single model prediction and the corresponding experimental VSD responses ranged from 0.040 to 0.071 for the sequence shown in panel (a), and from 0.015 to 0.035 for that in panel (b). This limited RMSE variability across slices suggests relative robustness of the model against biological variability.

IV. DISCUSSION

The present results demonstrate that the L–N modeling framework (Fig. 1) provides a useful approximation of cortical neural activity in response to retinal spike-timing-based microstimulation (Figs. 2 and 3). In particular, the model successfully captured

key aspects of the nonlinear relationship between the input spike trains and the output VSD responses.

The cortical slices used in this study differ structurally from *in-vivo* conditions due to dendritic damage and axonal transection, likely resulting in partial impairment of both excitatory and inhibitory synaptic transmission. To mitigate the influence of such disruptions, our analysis was restricted to neural responses recorded near the stimulating electrode. Although circuit integrity is compromised in slice preparations, the present L–N model may remain effective in capturing essential features of VSD response dynamics under *in-vivo* conditions as well.

For future clinical applications, species-specific differences must be addressed by adapting the model to human cortical dynamics. Although direct measurement of cortical circuit responses in humans is unfeasible, the visual cortices of rodents and primates share comparable hierarchical structures and connectivity patterns [8], supporting the potential of the proposed model—once appropriately modified and calibrated—to simulate human cortical responses and potentially guide quantitative optimization of stimulation protocols.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the current model does not incorporate activity-dependent changes such as use-dependent inactivation during repetitive stimulation [6], which may involve spike refractoriness, synaptic depletion, and recruitment of inhibitory circuits. These dynamics, together with short-term synaptic plasticity and recurrent network activity, are known to influence the temporal evolution of neural responses under sustained or high-frequency input conditions [9]. Consequently, the model may underestimate phenomena such as response attenuation or changes in time constants during prolonged stimulation. In addition, the L–N framework has limited capacity to reproduce the absolute amplitude of VSD responses, and additional normalization or scaling procedures may therefore be required for accurate quantitative comparisons. Future extensions of the model incorporating biophysically plausible mechanisms may further improve its ability to simulate cortical response dynamics under varied stimulation conditions.

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